

DESIGNING DIGITAL-METHODOLOGICAL SUPPORT FOR STUDENTS' PROFESSIONAL TRAINING

G.S. Xujaniyozova

Lecturer, Tashkent State University of Economics

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Abstract. *This article examines the design of digital-methodological support for preparing students for professional activity in the context of higher education digitalization. It identifies the pedagogical, methodological, digital, technical, ergonomic, and information-security requirements for developing digital educational resources, particularly in the teaching of mathematical disciplines with economic content. The study outlines key design principles, including integrativeness, professional and practical orientation, interactivity, visualization, individualization, independent knowledge acquisition, and collaborative work. It also defines the roles of teachers and students in using digital-methodological support to organize learning, assessment, feedback, and independent study. The proposed structure consists of target, methodological, content, technological, activity, control-and-assessment, and reflexive components. The article concludes that well-designed digital-methodological support strengthens interdisciplinary integration, improves students' digital competence, supports professional skill development, and enables teachers to manage, monitor, and enrich the educational process more effectively in response to the demands of a digital economy and modern professional education in practice today.*

Keywords: *digital-methodological support, digital-methodological support of the teacher, digital-methodological support of the student, target component, methodological component, content (information) component, technological component, activity component, control and evaluation component, reflexive component.*

1. Introduction

The rapid development of digital technologies and the digitalization of the economy require the system of preparing students for professional activity to be improved with due regard for the global trend of digitalization. Under conditions of digitalization, preparing students for professional activity is a multifaceted and complex process; these processes have required a reconsideration of the content and structure of student education, of pedagogical approaches, and the development of digital-methodological support (DMS).

In accordance with the “Digital Uzbekistan – 2030” strategy, developed pursuant to Decree No. PF–6079 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 5 October 2020, in order to enhance digital skills in the field of education, it is envisaged to implement the measure of “further improving electronic educational resources for the system of preschool, secondary and higher education, as well as ensuring access to domestic and global educational resources” [1].

We agree with V.M. Monakhov’s view that “it is impossible to achieve the intended pedagogical result without introducing into the educational process a large volume of information resources and universal skills for using them” [3].

In her article “Pedagogical communication in the electronic educational environment: research and educational approaches,” I.N. Rozina emphasizes that information educational

technologies should be understood as the application of information technologies to create new opportunities for transmitting knowledge (the teacher's activity), perceiving knowledge (the student's activity), assessing the quality of knowledge, and the comprehensive development of the student's personality in the educational process [4].

M.N. Skatkin stresses that methodological support is not only a certain system of materials but also a process. In other words, methodological support is the process of equipping activities within an educational program or module with the necessary methodological means that jointly ensure the achievement of the educational goal. Such materials include educational and monitoring materials, supplementary materials describing methods and forms of activity, communication, and so on [2].

By digital-methodological support (DMS) we understand the digital resources necessary for effectively organizing the educational process — including educational-normative, methodological, instructional, information-reference and control materials, pedagogical technologies, as well as electronic educational resources on educational platforms. It systematizes the processes of teaching, learning, assessment and analysis as an integrated whole.

All of the aforementioned components of digital-methodological support are applied in theoretical and practical classes and in organizing students' independent work. Under conditions of digitalization, digital-methodological support is an essential instrument of the educational process and, on the basis of integrating pedagogical and information-communication technologies, organizes an effective learning environment.

2. Methods

Designing digital-methodological support is the process of preparing the electronic learning materials, interactive resources, and assessment and control tools necessary for effectively organizing the educational process, and of systematizing and integrating the use of existing software resources, educational platforms, electronic libraries, scientific databases, and online courses. This process makes it possible to mathematically model economic problems on the basis of digital technologies.

The following principal tasks of designing digital-methodological support were defined: identifying the digital technologies used in teaching mathematical disciplines; updating the subject syllabus and the fund of assessment tools on the basis of digital technologies; preparing electronic learning materials; developing a system of subject-based problems, professionally oriented problems, and situational problems with economic content; preparing interactive models and simulations that allow economic processes to be analyzed and forecast in a digital environment; and implementing a system for organizing and assessing students' independent learning online.

In designing the DMS for preparing students for professional activity in the teaching of mathematics, priority was given to the following principles, which, together with general didactic principles, also encompass profession-specific features:

- **Principle of integrativeness** — within the DMS, the content of educational knowledge is presented through electronic textbooks, study guides and integrative dictionaries that are illuminated on the basis of interdisciplinary connections;
- **Principle of professional orientation** — enriching the learning materials with economic knowledge, for example, by providing problems with economic content concerning supply and demand in the market and finding the surplus of the consumer and the supplier. This

is aimed at forming in students the skills and competencies to apply acquired knowledge in professional activity;

- **Principle of practical orientation** — attention is focused on digital educational resources aimed at forming economic-mathematical modeling skills, for example, analyzing economic processes through interdisciplinary projects;
- **Principle of interactivity** — denotes the collaborative cooperation of subject (teacher) – object (DMS) – subject (student), for example, students exchanging views on educational platforms when analyzing economic situations during independent learning;
- **Principle of visualization** — illustrative modeling of economic processes by means of diagrams and graphs helps to understand the essence of economic processes;
- **Principle of individualization** — digital platforms provide tasks corresponding to students' level of mastery;
- **Principle of independent acquisition of knowledge** — DMS resources must give the student the opportunity to acquire knowledge independently and to self-assess;
- **Principle of collaborative work** — relations among the subjects of the educational process based on mutual accord and trust in achieving a common goal, for example, online conferences.

For the teaching of mathematical disciplines, we identified the following requirements for developing the digital educational resources (DER) within professionally oriented digital-methodological support built on interdisciplinary integration:

- **Scientific-methodological requirements** — the DER must be based on modern scientific achievements and conform to the syllabus; in modeling economic processes, concepts, methods, algorithms and models must be correctly formulated and strictly mathematically accurate;
- **Pedagogical requirements** — reliance on the principles of systematicity, continuity, consistency, integrity, and practical and professional orientation; developing creative, analytical and algorithmic thinking in analyzing economic processes; using interactive teaching models; conformity of the structure of the digital-methodological support to the structure of the didactic teaching cycle: theory, practice, independent work, control;
- **Methodological requirements** — continuity of the learning materials; mutual coherence of theoretical and practical classes and independent-learning materials; a system of tasks of varying levels: subject-based problems, professionally oriented problems, and situational problems with economic content; clarity of assessment criteria;
- **Digital requirements** — conformity of the DER to the capabilities of modern computer graphics; interactive models, simulation (visualization of learning materials), automation of computations, and automation of the control-and-assessment process;
- **Technical requirements** — stable operation on technical devices, a convenient and user-friendly interface, and the use of multimedia elements;
- **Information-security and data-reliability requirements** — use of reliable sources, and measures against technical failures and viruses;
- **Ergonomic requirements** — for organizing dialogue; for the visual environment; for text format and knowledge parameters; hypertext for introducing multimedia technologies; telecommunications; and reflective audio-video features, including the features of graphical information.

3. Results

In developing the digital-methodological support, the teacher prepares electronic learning materials and designs the educational process on the basis of integrating pedagogical and digital technologies. The teacher's activities in developing the digital-methodological support are as follows:

- **develops the subject syllabus:** plans the learning outcomes, develops assessment criteria, defines the competencies, and selects the content of the learning materials;
- **designs the learning materials:** creating an electronic textbook, electronic lectures, online tests, presentations and video lessons; studying the mathematical models of economic processes; developing a set of subject-based and situational problems and individual tasks, and creating their electronic version;
- **selects digital resources:** computer mathematics systems, visualization tools, educational platforms, and websites;
- **organizes interactive teaching:** preparing electronic interdisciplinary crosswords and integrative dictionaries, organizing business games connected with problematic economic situations, developing and conducting interdisciplinary project topics, holding online olympiads and conferences, and developing materials for the student's independent work;
- **assessment** — develops control materials and conducts monitoring and analysis on the basis of assessment criteria, for example, developing automated tests;
- **methodological support:** preparing guidelines for independent learning and organizing consultations for students;
- **reflection:** continuously studying students' feedback in order to analyze the effectiveness of the digital-methodological support, and updating and enriching the digital educational resources.

On the basis of the above, we define the content of the digital-methodological support of the teacher and of the student in preparing students for professional activity.

The teacher's digital-methodological support is a set of methodological developments, electronic learning materials, interactive exercises, software resources, educational platforms, electronic libraries, scientific databases, online courses, and assessment and control tools that make it possible to organize the educational process at a high level, to gain rapid access to information, and to organize, manage and control interactive teaching.

The student's digital-methodological support is a set of methodological support, educational information resources, interactive learning tools, software tools, educational platforms, electronic libraries, online courses, and assessment and control tools designed to enable the student to study effectively in the educational process, to acquire knowledge independently, and to develop professional competencies.

Digital-methodological support helps the student to apply mathematical models in studying general-professional disciplines and in future professional activity, and helps the teacher to develop the skills of using a system of professionally oriented integrative knowledge in teaching mathematics.

The content of the digital-methodological support comprises the following components, each of which performs specific tasks:

Target component. It defines the general aims and tasks of education, encompassing the subject program (syllabus), the educational goal, the competencies, and the learning outcomes.

Methodological component. Methodological guidelines for students on mastering the subject, diagnostics of learning opportunities, instructions for completing independent learning, assessment criteria, and discussion of the types of activity in teaching. It helps the student to correctly organize their activity in the educational process.

Content (information) component. It is oriented toward forming competencies in the subject and ensures the student's acquisition of knowledge. The content (information) component consists of the following blocks: theoretical and practical knowledge (electronic textbook, electronic guide, video lectures, multimedia materials, models, tests) and interactive materials (integrative dictionary, presentations, infographics, simulations).

Technological component. Software resources, videoconferencing tools, educational platforms, electronic libraries, scientific databases, and online courses. In the technological component, the teacher uses platforms to organize the educational process and the student uses them to acquire knowledge. It ensures communication between the teacher and the student.

Activity component. It is oriented toward developing competencies in the subject. The activity component consists of the following blocks: creating digital content, materials for self-instruction (solving subject-based and situational problems, creating digital content, solving crosswords, business games), online consultations, conducting online olympiads and conferences, sending electronic messages, working on educational platforms, in electronic libraries and scientific databases, participating in remote olympiads and conferences, and acquiring knowledge on educational platforms, in electronic libraries and online courses.

Control-and-assessment component. It determines the effectiveness of teaching and identifies and assesses the student's level of knowledge. The control-and-assessment component consists of the following blocks: individual tasks, tests, situational problems and interdisciplinary projects across the types of assessment (current, intermediate (independent learning), final).

Reflexive component. The reflexive component serves to compare goals with learning outcomes (self-assessment, analysis and conclusion), to set new goals for developing competencies, and to improve the educational process.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

Organizing the educational process under conditions of using digital-methodological support ensures interdisciplinary integration and raises the level of development of the student's digital competence. The proposed structure of digital-methodological support — with its target, methodological, content, technological, activity, control-and-assessment and reflexive components — makes it possible to systematize, as an integrated whole, the activities of both the teacher and the student in preparing students for professional activity, and to bring the teaching of mathematical disciplines into line with the demands of a digitalizing economy.

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